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NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

PILOT CREDIT

[SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 14

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Contents

1. INTRODUCTION	3
2. METHODOLOGY	3
3. PILOT CREDIT: TELEWORKING ENVIRONMENT	5
3.1 Purpose	5
3.2 Applicability	5
3.3 Requirements	6
3.4 Verification	6
3.5 Table	7
4. PILOT CREDIT APPLICATION	8
4.1 Case study 1	8
4.1.1 Ergonomics and Safety	9
4.1.2 Environmental comfort	10
4.1.3 Air exchange and ventilation	11
4.1.4 Acoustics	11
4.1.5 Lighting and visual comfort	11
4.1.6 Biophilia	12
4.1.7 Connectivity and equipment	12
4.1.8 Requirements verification and improvement actions	12
4.2 Case study 2	13
4.2.1 Ergonomics and Safety	13
4.2.2 Environmental comfort	15
4.2.3 Air exchange and ventilation	15
4.2.4 Acoustics	16
4.2.5 Lighting and visual comfort	16
4.2.6 Biophilia	17
4.2.7 Connectivity and equipment	17
4.2.8 Requirements verification and improvement actions	17
5. CONCLUSIONS	18
6. ANNEXES	20
7. GLOSSARY	20
8. REFERENCES	21

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable presents the development of a Pilot Credit for the indoor environmental quality assessment of teleworking spaces. The work stems from the need to develop a practical and evidence-based framework for evaluating the quality of indoor environments increasingly used for teleworking. Remote and hybrid work models have consolidated as a structural component of professional life, bringing renewed attention to the role of both physical settings and digital infrastructures in supporting productivity, wellbeing, and sustainability. However, the tools currently available within building certification schemes remain primarily oriented toward conventional office or institutional buildings, leaving a gap in relation to emerging work practices and the spaces where they take place. To address this gap, the research first carried out a review of internationally recognized standards and methodological references, which were organized into a theoretical evaluation table. This preparatory step provided a comprehensive framework for systematizing relevant criteria. Building on this foundation, the study developed an exemplary Pilot Credit, conceived as a concise and operational tool for assessing public, semi-public, and non-domestic private spaces for teleworking.

The Pilot Credit is not intended as a definitive protocol, but as an experimental contribution that can inform both practice and policy. While autonomous in its design, it may also serve as a potential complement to existing sustainability and wellbeing certification systems, and as a starting point for future standardization.

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted for this work was oriented from the beginning to the definition of a Pilot Credit for teleworking environments.

The process started with a review of international standards and protocols on environmental quality and workplace wellbeing. The main references were:

- the *WELL Building Standard™ version 2 (WELL v2)* [1], which provides a comprehensive framework on indoor environmental quality, comfort, and mental health;

- the *Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design version 4.1 for Building Design and Construction (LEED v4.1 BD+C)* [2], particularly credits related to indoor air quality, daylight, and energy monitoring;
- the *Green Building Council Italia (GBC Italia)* documentation [3] [4], including the Pilot Credit 106 – Biophilia; The latter, although conceived as an autonomous contribution and not directly included within the GBC protocols, nonetheless retains the institutional authorship of GBC Italia, thus representing a complementary and consistent reference within the adopted methodological framework.
- the *European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA) Telework Checklist* [5], which proved especially valuable for its clarity, practical relevance, and applicability to everyday working conditions.

These references provided both technically rigorous criteria (indoor air quality, comfort, energy monitoring, biophilia, acoustic, lighting) and practical indications directly related to remote working (ergonomics, digital connectivity, workload management).

From this review, a theoretical evaluation table was drafted and is reported in Annex A. Its purpose was not to propose a definitive tool, but rather to organize the selected criteria into thematic categories (indoor air quality, thermal comfort, acoustic comfort, visual comfort, smart technologies, interaction and belonging). For each subcategory, the table reports references, scope, minimum requirements, and interpretative notes. The criteria in this table were selected but not reinterpreted, in order to preserve their original meaning and ensure alignment with authoritative sources.

As a preparatory step, the theoretical table provides a broad and systematic framework. The Pilot Credit developed in the next section, instead, results from an interpretative process aimed at producing a tool that is more concise, effective, and directly applicable to teleworking environments.

The framework is conceived to support professionals, designers, employers, and individual workers in assessing their workspaces in a systematic yet flexible way. By combining measurable parameters with subjective aspects such as perceived comfort, personalization, and connection to nature, it provides a comprehensive and accessible tool for the evaluation and transformation of remote work environments.

The theoretical evaluation table developed in this phase is reported in Annex A, where all selected criteria are summarized and organized by thematic category. For completeness, Annex B reports the source of original credits.

3. PILOT CREDIT: TELEWORKING ENVIRONMENT

The Pilot Credit presented in this section is the result of an interpretative process derived from the research carried out in the previous section. Not all the categories identified during the theoretical phase have been included in the interpretative evaluation table, since the intention was to design a tool that is concise, effective, and directly applicable to real teleworking environments.

In particular, categories more closely related to social interaction and psychological aspects were excluded from the present framework. These themes, while highly relevant, are only partially addressed here and will require complementary tools or dedicated studies to be fully integrated. The resulting evaluation sheet therefore concentrates on the most tangible and measurable dimensions of teleworking environments, ensuring clarity, practicality, and ease of application.

3.1 Purpose

The Pilot Credit aims to promote and qualify the availability of teleworking-ready spaces by ensuring environmental, ergonomic and technological conditions that foster wellbeing, productivity and safety across three context types: public spaces, semi-public spaces (privately owned but open to users), and non-domestic private spaces (access-controlled, e.g., company premises). The extension preserves the credit's concise, operational nature and its emphasis on measurable requirements and potential integration into existing schemes..

3.2 Applicability

The Pilot Credit applies to existing environments intended for teleworking in the following categories:

1. **Public spaces:** publicly owned/managed and freely accessible environments (e.g., civic libraries, institutional venues, multifunctional halls).
2. **Semi-public spaces:** privately owned environments open to users (e.g., coworking spaces, mixed-use venues, shared condominium areas, privately managed facilities with public access).

3. **Non-domestic private spaces:** privately owned workplaces used internally by an organization and not open to the general public (e.g., offices and company premises reserved for employees and authorized guests), where the organization intends to designate specific workstations/areas for telework or hybrid work.

This choice is driven by operational and methodological considerations:

- Purpose: the intent is not to regulate home offices or private domestic spaces, but to promote and qualify remote-working stations within collective and/or organizational contexts: public spaces, semi-public spaces (privately owned but open to users), and non-domestic private spaces (access-controlled, e.g., company premises). The Pilot Credit is therefore oriented toward environments where requirements can be objectively assessed and managed, while domestic settings remain outside the current scope due to privacy protections and the impracticality of continuous monitoring.
- Verifiability: in such environments, requirements can be measured and documented (surveys, technical datasheets, maintenance plans, connectivity reports), ensuring transparency and consistency.
- Governance: public, semi-public, and non-domestic private spaces are managed by responsible entities (public authorities, operators/administrators, employers or facility managers) capable of ensuring compliance and long-term maintenance.

Accordingly, the Pilot Credit is applicable to public spaces, semi-public spaces, and non-domestic private spaces, with the sole exclusion of domestic residential settings. The current priority is to consolidate its application in these verifiable and governed contexts, where certification can generate broader social, community, and organizational impact.

3.3 Requirements

To obtain the credit, at least 5 out of 9 objectives must be met. The requirements are organized into four themes:

- Ergonomics and safety;
- Environmental comfort;
- Biophilia;
- Connectivity and equipment.

3.4 Verification

For each requirement met, provide at least one of the following forms of evidence:

- Functional layouts and space plans;
- Georeferenced or dated photographs;
- Technical datasheets of furniture and systems;
- Instrumental surveys (photometric, acoustic, hygro-thermal measurements);
- Technical report on network and connectivity;
- Green maintenance plan.

3.5 Table

Theme	Code	Objective	Requirements	References
1. Ergonomics and Safety	1.1	Workstation Furniture	- ≥50% of workstations with adjustable seating (height, backrest, lumbar support) - Tables with height 70–76 cm, depth ≥75 cm, leg clearance ≥60 cm - Layout compliant with ergonomic principles (VDT, space, posture)	[6]
	1.2	Electrical safety and accessibility	- No loose cables; CEI-compliant sockets; accessible switches - Smoke detectors; barrier-free accessible routes - Compliance with relevant electrical and accessibility regulations	[8] [9] [10]
2. Environmental Comfort	2.1	Thermal Comfort	Indoor operative temperature shall comply with UNI EN 16798-1:2019, Category III: - Winter (heated buildings): 19.0–25.0 °C - Summer (cooled buildings): 22.0–27.0 °C - Relative humidity recommended between 20–70% - Indoor air speed: ≤ 0.15 m/s (winter), ≤ 0.25 m/s (summer) or, in the absence of air conditioning systems: adaptive criteria from UNI EN 16798-1:2019	[11] [12] [13] [14]
	2.2	Air exchange and ventilation	- Mechanical ventilation compliant with UNI EN 16798-1:2019, ensuring outdoor air supply ≥ Category II (according to use); - If no mechanical ventilation is provided, continuous CO ₂ monitoring must be installed to verify indoor air quality.	[15] [16]

	2.3	Acoustics	- Ambient noise ≤ 42 dB(A) - Reverberation time $< 0,8$ s	[17] [18] [19] [20]
	2.4	Lighting and visual comfort	- Illuminance ≥ 500 lux on the work plane - Daylight factor $\geq 2\%$ - At least 75% of workstations shall provide a direct view to the outdoors, with the line of sight to the exterior available at an eye level of at least 1.1 m above floor level. - Emergency escape lighting luminaires shall be positioned to ensure a minimum vertical illuminance of 5 lx at the location of each piece of firefighting equipment and at every fire alarm call point - Artificial lighting in workspaces shall provide a general colour rendering index (Ra) of at least 80, ensuring natural and accurate rendering of objects and materials.	[21] [22] [23] [24]
3. Biophilia	3.1	Indoor vegetation	Vegetation present in at least 65% of regularly occupied rooms, with minimum 1 plant per room	[25]
4. Connectivity and equipment	4.1	Network access	Free WiFi in $\geq 90\%$ of the usable area; guaranteed minimum bandwidth ≥ 20 Mbps download.	[26]
	4.2	Accessory equipment	$\geq 50\%$ of workstations with power outlets, desk lamp, ≥ 1 m ² of free surface; availability of alternative/relax seating; presence of smoke detectors in the environment.	[5] [27]

4. PILOT CREDIT APPLICATION

4.1 Case study 1

As an example, this section reports the analysis carried out at Politecnico di Torino on a study/work area equipped with multiple workstations, located in front of the meeting room FTA – I.5/P.2 – DENERG South. Measurements were performed during a summer day; therefore, the assessment of thermal comfort refers to summer conditions and related comfort categories. The analyzed area is a connective space of approximately 20 m², furnished with 8 individual seating workstations. Figure 1 reports the layout of the area under investigation and photographs documenting its current configuration.

Figure 1 – Plan and photographs of the analyzed space.

4.1.1 Ergonomics and Safety

Workstation furniture

The 8 workstations are equipped with adjustable seating and tables with a height between 72–75 cm. The worktop dimensions (90 × 160 cm) and leg clearance are adequate. Figure 2 illustrates the layout and furniture arrangement of the analyzed space.

→ **Requirement satisfied**

Fig. 2 – Furniture present in the space

Electrical safety and accessibility

The power outlets are distributed through compliant power strips and no loose cables are present on the floor. A smoke detector is installed in the environment.

→ **Requirement satisfied.**

4.1.2 Environmental comfort

Thermal comfort

Instrumental measurements were taken at three points in the room during a representative summer day. In the morning, indoor air temperature ranged between 26.6 °C and 27.2 °C, with relative humidity between 90% and 97.1%. In the afternoon, temperatures ranged between 27.2 °C and 27.9 °C, with relative humidity between 90% and 99.5%. Air speed was measured at the same points, but the instrument did not detect significant movement, resulting in approximately 0.0 m/s.

According to standards, thermal comfort categories are defined differently: **UNI EN ISO 7730:2005** identifies Categories A, B, and C, while **UNI EN 16798-1:2019** refers to Categories I, II, III, and IV. In this Pilot Credit, the target requirement corresponds to **Category B (ISO 7730) / Category III (UNI EN 16798-1)**, considered suitable for office-type and teleworking environments.

Based on the collected data, conditions do not comply with the thermal comfort parameters for the target category, since both indoor temperature and relative humidity exceed the recommended summer limits. These values may result in warm thermal discomfort for occupants, leading to a high risk of thermal stress and reduced productivity

→ **Requirement not satisfied.**

4.1.3 Air exchange and ventilation

The space is equipped with openable windows on only one side, which provide partial and non-cross *airing*. A summer air-conditioning system is present, but no mechanical ventilation with controlled air exchange is installed, nor are systems for monitoring CO₂ concentration available.

In light of these conditions, the environment does not meet the minimum requirements set by UNI EN 16798-1:2019 for workplace ventilation, neither in terms of airflow nor indoor air quality control. The absence of both mechanical ventilation and CO₂ monitoring reduces the effectiveness of air renewal and does not allow verification of indoor quality during extended occupancy periods.

→ **Requirement not satisfied.**

4.1.4 Acoustics

Spot acoustic monitoring was carried out with the windows kept closed, measuring reverberation times (RT60 – T20) across bands from 125 Hz to 8000 Hz. The results show an average reverberation time of 0.49 seconds, with variations between 0.35 s and 0.56 s, within the recommended limits for spaces intended for individual or concentration activities.

The background noise level was recorded at 39.5 dBA Leq (10 minutes), consistent with low-noise environments and fully compliant with UNI 11532-2:2020 and UNI EN ISO 3382-2:2008 for study or teleworking spaces.

→ **Requirement satisfied.**

4.1.5 Lighting and visual comfort

Illuminance measurements were performed at three sample workstations under natural light conditions only, yielding values of 40 lux, 90 lux, and 280 lux. Since simultaneous outdoor illuminance was not recorded, the Daylight Factor (DF) was calculated by adopting the conventional CIE overcast sky assumption of $E_{out} = 10,000$ lx. The corresponding DF values are 0.4%, 0.9%, and 2.8%. Only one workstation achieves $DF \geq 2\%$, while the average value (1.37%) remains below the required threshold.

The space benefits from natural light from a single windowed wall, but overall daylight availability does not comply with the target requirement of $DF \geq 2\%$. Moreover, the environment lacks both desk lamps and localized artificial lighting systems that could compensate for insufficient daylight contribution. The external view is also inadequate, as

it is not available for at least 75% of the workstations, thus missing a key element for visual comfort and connection to the external environment.

→ **Requirement not satisfied.**

4.1.6 Biophilia

Indoor vegetation

The environment does not contain any vegetation or ornamental plants. No maintenance plan for greenery or integration of biophilic elements is foreseen.

→ **Requirement not satisfied.**

4.1.7 Connectivity and equipment

Network access

The room is covered by a public WiFi network, with tested bandwidth of 42 Mbps download and 9 Mbps upload during peak hours.

→ **Requirement satisfied.**

Accessory equipment

One electrical outlet is available for every two workstations. However, no desk lamps or alternative seating are provided.

→ **Requirement not satisfied.**

4.1.8 Requirements verification and improvement actions

Total score obtained: 4 out of 9

Outcome: **CREDIT NOT ATTRIBUTED**

Recommended improvement actions:

- Address thermal comfort issues as a priority, since excessive indoor temperature and relative humidity represent the main source of discomfort and significantly reduce productivity. Corrective measures should be considered already at the design and planning phase, such as the introduction of adequate mechanical ventilation or improved cooling strategies.
- Add individual desk lamps at each workstation to improve artificial lighting.
- Introduce vegetation elements (at least 1 plant every 25 m²) and define a weekly maintenance plan.
- Install a CO₂ measuring device to allow verification of indoor air quality in the absence of mechanical ventilation.
- Provide alternative seating (e.g., stools, soft seating, relaxation areas) to diversify

ergonomics.

This example demonstrates the potential for enhancing and qualifying existing public spaces through both targeted design measures and minimal interventions, combined with an assessment based on simple yet systematic measurements. The introduction of additional equipment (individual lighting, biophilic furnishings, alternative seating) would allow for further improvements, while design-level actions on ventilation and thermal regulation remain crucial for ensuring long-term comfort and productivity.

4.2 Case study 2

As a second example, this section reports the analysis conducted at Politecnico di Torino on the Cafaro room, a meeting space used by Acoustics researchers, professors and PhD students. Measurements were carried out under winter conditions; therefore, the thermal comfort assessment refers to winter conditions and related comfort categories. The Cafaro room is located on the second floor of the DENERG Department and is mainly used for research group meetings. The room accommodates approximately 31 upholstered seats, distributed between the speakers' area and the audience.

The floor is covered with linoleum and all walls are plastered; on one side, eight small windows arranged in two blocks are placed very low, close to the floor. The vaulted ceiling, characterized by truss beams, gives the room a distinctive shape that also affects its acoustic behavior. Several large tables and two wall-mounted TV screens are available and are regularly used for conferences and hybrid meetings.

Figure 3 reports the layout of the Cafaro room and photographs documenting its current configuration.

4.2.1 Ergonomics and Safety

Workstation furniture

The room is furnished with rectangular tables measuring approximately 160 cm by 90 cm, each used by two people along the long side. The height is around 72–74 cm and ensures adequate leg clearance and work surface for laptops, documents and small devices.

Users sit on upholstered chairs with backrest and armrests, which provide sufficient support for typical meeting durations and allow a generally neutral sitting posture. The tables are arranged in rows with appropriate spacing, so that users can access their seats and move within the room without obstructions.

→ **Requirement satisfied**

Figure 3 – Plan and photographs of the analyzed space.

Fig. 4 – Furniture present in the space

Electrical safety and accessibility

The power outlets are distributed through compliant power strips and no loose cables are present on the floor. A smoke detector is installed in the environment.

→ **Requirement satisfied.**

4.2.2 Environmental comfort

Thermal comfort

Indoor measurements were carried out at four points in the occupied zone during a typical winter use of the Cafaro room. Air temperature ranged between 19.4 °C and 20.0 °C, with an average value of about 19.7 °C. Relative humidity varied from approximately 50% to 78%, with an average of about 65%. Dew point and wet-bulb temperature values are consistent with these conditions, while air speed was negligible (0 m/s) in all points, indicating absence of draughts in the seating area.

Overall, the measured parameters fall within acceptable ranges for a meeting room in winter conditions, ensuring a generally comfortable thermal environment for the occupants.

→ **Requirement satisfied.**

4.2.3 Air exchange and ventilation

The Cafaro room is naturally ventilated through three roof skylights and two large operable windows along one of the long sides. The combination of façade openings and skylights enables stack-driven air movement between the lower and upper parts of the room, providing natural cross-ventilation when the openings are used during occupancy and improving perceived air freshness for teleworking activities.

However, no mechanical ventilation system designed according to UNI EN 16798-1:2019 is installed, and continuous monitoring of indoor CO₂ concentration is not provided. As a

result, air-change rates and compliance with the minimum outdoor air supply specified by the requirements cannot be systematically verified during prolonged use of the space.

→ **Requirement not satisfied.**

4.2.4 Acoustics

Reverberation time (T_{20} , unoccupied) was measured in the Cafaro room in the 125–8000 Hz octave bands, with the heating system switched off and all windows closed during the measurements. In the main speech frequency range (125–2000 Hz) values are generally around 1.0 s and remain above 0.8 s, indicating a rather reverberant acoustic environment. At higher frequencies, reverberation time decreases but only approaches 0.8 s in the 8000 Hz band.

Background noise level was measured over a 15-minute interval under typical conditions of use, resulting in an equivalent continuous level of approximately 37 dB(A), thus complying with the limit of 42 dB(A) specified by the requirements. Although the background noise criterion is satisfied, the reverberation time target is not met, suggesting limited control of sound reflections and a possible reduction in speech intelligibility

→ **Requirement not satisfied**

4.2.5 Lighting and visual comfort

Illuminance on the work plane was assessed at four representative workstations in the Cafaro room (754 lx, 514 lx, 471 lx and 429 lx), with an average of approximately 540 lx. This mean value is above the 500 lx target for teleworking, supporting clear readability of both screens and printed materials. Although illuminance varies across positions, all points remain within ranges typically recommended for indoor workspaces, with no clearly under-lit stations.

Daylight is provided by three skylights and by windows along one wall; however, due to their relatively low placement, not all desks benefit from a direct outdoor view at seated eye level. Electric lighting is supplied by LED luminaires, offering good colour rendering for people, furniture and materials. Emergency luminaires are installed along escape routes and near firefighting equipment and alarm call points, ensuring adequate vertical illuminance in these critical areas.

Overall, the combination of adequate average task illuminance, appropriate artificial-light quality and dedicated emergency lighting indicates that the lighting and visual comfort requirement for teleworking activities in the Cafaro room can be considered satisfied.

→ **Requirement satisfied.**

4.2.6 Biophilia

Indoor vegetation

The environment does not contain any vegetation or ornamental plants. No maintenance plan for greenery or integration of biophilic elements is foreseen.

→ **Requirement not satisfied.**

4.2.7 Connectivity and equipment

Network access

The room is covered by a public WiFi network, with tested bandwidth of 45 Mbps download and 11 Mbps upload during peak hours.

→ **Requirement satisfied.**

Accessory equipment

One electrical outlet is available for every workstations. However, no desk lamps or alternative seating are provided.

→ **Requirement not satisfied.**

4.2.8 Requirements verification and improvement actions

Total score obtained: 5 out of 9

Outcome: **CREDIT ATTRIBUTED**

The Cafaro room meets the minimum threshold of the Pilot Credit, satisfying the objectives related to workstation furniture, electrical safety, thermal comfort, lighting and visual comfort, and network access. On the other hand, air exchange and ventilation, acoustic performance, biophilia and accessory equipment do not fully comply with the defined requirements and represent the main areas for improvement.

Recommended improvement actions:

- Improve air exchange and ventilation by introducing a mechanical ventilation system designed according to UNI EN 16798-1:2019, or, where this is not immediately feasible, by installing continuous CO₂ monitoring and defining clear airing protocols for the use of façade windows and skylights.

- Enhance acoustic comfort through the addition of sound-absorbing materials (e.g., acoustic panels on walls and/or ceiling, curtains, soft furnishings) in order to reduce reverberation time in the main speech frequency range and improve speech intelligibility during teleworking and hybrid activities.
- Introduce indoor vegetation and biophilic elements, for example by adding plants and small green arrangements and defining a simple maintenance plan, to improve perceived environmental quality and visual comfort.
- Upgrade accessory equipment by providing desk lamps at workstations, increasing the number of easily accessible power outlets where needed, and integrating alternative seating options (e.g., stools, soft seating or small lounge corners) to diversify postures and support different teleworking tasks.

These measures would consolidate the positive aspects already present in the Cafaro room and progressively transform it into a more complete and versatile teleworking environment, while maintaining the relatively limited scale and reversibility of the interventions.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable has presented the development of a Pilot Credit for assessing the environmental quality of teleworking spaces located in public facilities, semi-public venues, and non-domestic private premises. Starting from a review of international standards and protocols, a theoretical evaluation framework was drafted and then distilled into a concise and operational Pilot Credit, supported by two application examples. The outcome is not a protocol specifically designed for existing certification schemes (e.g., WELL, LEED, GBC), but an autonomous tool that may in the future be integrated into them. Its added value lies in addressing the specific conditions of teleworking in verifiable and governed contexts, public, semi-public, and non-domestic private spaces, which are increasingly central for community wellbeing and sustainable territorial development.

Looking ahead, the evolution of the Pilot Credit could follow a progressive roadmap (Figure 3), articulated into four main steps:

Step 1 – Validation (short term). The immediate priority is to apply the Pilot Credit to real case studies, such as public libraries, multifunctional community spaces, or shared facilities. This phase will allow testing the clarity and feasibility of the requirements,

collecting feedback from managers and users, and refining both criteria and verification methods on the basis of practical experience.

Step 2 – Consolidation (medium term). Once validated, the Pilot Credit will be consolidated through the development of guidance documents and checklists that support its application in small-scale contexts. At this stage, optional “levels of verification” basic or advanced could be introduced, to balance methodological rigor with broader scalability. Promotion of adoption by municipalities, public authorities, and community organizations will be key to ensure real territorial impact.

Step 3 – Integration and Synergies (medium–long term). In a subsequent phase, the Pilot Credit will benefit from collaborations with project partners and other Work Packages (WP) within the NODES initiative, fostering alignment with strategies on digital innovation, wellbeing, and sustainability. At the same time, synergies with local and regional policies for smart working and territorial development will be explored. This will also include the evaluation of possible integration into international certification systems (e.g., WELL, LEED, GBC) as a complementary or pilot credit.

Step 4 – Standardization (long term). Finally, efforts will be directed toward engaging with national and international standardization bodies (UNI, ISO, GBC Italia, IWBI) to discuss pathways for official recognition. This stage will work toward including teleworking environmental quality into mainstream building certification systems. Dissemination of results and publication of guidelines will support replication and large-scale adoption.

Through this roadmap, the Pilot Credit can move from being a research output to becoming a replicable and recognized tool, capable of generating concrete impact on communities, territories, and certification practices.

Figure 5 – Roadmap for the Pilot Credit.

Progressive steps for future development: validation, consolidation, integration, and standardization.

6. ANNEXES

The Table reported in Annex A summarizes all the criteria that were selected for further analysis. In Annex B, all the original sources of credits are reported.

7. GLOSSARY

- **WELL (WELL Building Standard v2):** international certification system developed by IWBI, focused on health, wellbeing, and environmental quality in buildings.
- **LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design v4.1):** international certification system by USGBC, addressing sustainability and energy efficiency in building design and construction.
- **GBC Italia (Green Building Council Italia):** national association that develops and promotes environmental certification protocols adapted to the Italian context.
- **EU-OSHA (European Agency for Safety and Health at Work):** European agency providing guidelines and checklists for occupational health and safety, including teleworking.
- **UNI (Ente Nazionale Italiano di Unificazione):** Italian national body for standardization, issuing technical standards (Norme UNI).
- **ISO (International Organization for Standardization):** international body that develops and publishes global standards for technology, safety, and quality.

- **CEI (Comitato Elettrotecnico Italiano):** Italian body responsible for electrical and electronic technical standards.
- **ANSI/ASHRAE:** American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers, developer of standards on thermal comfort and indoor environmental quality.
- **WP (Work Package):** operational unit within the NODES project structure, grouping activities and partners around specific themes.
- **Pilot Credit:** an experimental credit, designed as a potential add-on to building certification schemes, used to test innovative evaluation criteria before standardization.

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